

MITIGATION POTENTIAL OF CLIMATE SMART ACTIONS – an assessment of the potential of different soils for CH₄ uptake and C sequestration based on laboratory incubations

Anna Walkiewicz¹, Gerardo Moreno², María Vivas², Víctor Rolo²

¹ Institute of Agrophysics, Polish Academy of Sciences, Lublin, Poland

² Forest Research Group, INDEHESA, University of Extremadura, Plasencia, Spain

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17465261

Rationale

The use of different agricultural practices affects carbon (C) cycling and may improve C sequestration. Among greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation practices, it is also worth recognizing those that have the potential to increase the ability of soils to methane (CH₄) consumption known as process of methanotrophy. The activity of methanotrophic bacteria in the soil results in the oxidation of CH₄ to CO₂ and H₂O, which is regulated by edaphic conditions. The process of soil methanotrophy contributes to the reduction of CH₄ concentrations in the atmosphere (high-affinity methanotrophy), but may also mitigate CH₄ emissions via microbial oxidation of elevated subsurface CH₄ concentrations prior to atmospheric release (low-affinity methanotrophy) (Walkiewicz et al. 2020). Increased soil methanotrophy activity can improve the C balance, which is particularly important on livestock farms that are a source of CH₄ due to enteric fermentation and manure management (Maze et al. 2024). Both C sequestration and the ability of soils to absorb CH₄ can be increased by improving soil conditions, among addition of biochar to soils showing potential to facilitate these processes. Due to its many benefits, biochar is even described as a soil amendment in Climate-Smart Agriculture (Bhattacharyya et al. 2024). Although the production of biochar through the pyrolysis of waste biomass is part of the circular economy, the effects of using this additive depend on many factors and are still under discussion. There are many recognized benefits to applying biochar to soil, but there are still many challenges associated with standardizing its use (Schmidt et al. 2021).

Aim of the laboratory studies

The aim of the laboratory studies was to assess the effect of different soil additives (different biochars and crop residues with potential of climate change mitigation) on CH₄ uptake (soil methanotrophy) and edaphic conditions, including organic C content and soil microorganisms community. Conducting lab incubation of soils under controlled moisture and temperature conditions, allows for an overview of the mechanisms behind the observed effects.

Experiment design and methodology

Initially, the basic characteristics of representative soil samples were measured, including pH, organic C and total N contents, and soil texture based on the particle size distribution. Soil incubations were prepared in accordance with the previously adopted procedure (e.g., Walkiewicz et al. 2020; Kubaczyński et al. 2022). Soil samples were placed into 20 cm³ bottles, enriched with selected additive at the established dose (converted to Mg/ha), and left for about one month for soil microorganisms acclimatization (in the dark, at a temperature of 25°C). Control samples were soil without any additive. Next, the soil moisture was adjusted to 60% (optimal for microbial processes) or 100% (saturated conditions) water holding capacity (WHC) by addition of appropriate volumes of distilled water, and after ventilation and closing the vials with rubber stoppers and aluminum caps, the headspace was enriched with 1% of CH₄ (v/v). The soil samples were incubated in dark at a temperature of 25°C, and changes in CH₄ concentration were determined regularly every 2-3 days using a gas chromatograph (Shimadzu, Japan), fitted with a flame ionization detector (FID) for analysis of CH₄. Helium was used as a carrier gas. At the end of incubation, the bottles were opened to measure soil pH and organic C content, and to collect soil samples for isolation of DNA to recognize general microbial community including methanotrophic bacteria (especially in variants where additives used significantly changed soil CH₄ uptake rate).

Fig. 1. General scheme of the experiments.

Standardized and generally accepted methods were used for soil measurements:

- WHC - by determining water content in a water-saturated soil sample after gravitational water drainage,
- pH - potentiometrically in soil and water slurry, with a ratio of soil: 1:2.5 w/w,
- organic C - combustion using a TOC analyser,
- total N – Kjeldahl method,
- particle size distribution – the laser diffraction method,
- soil microbial biomass – based on CO₂ emission after glucose addition,
- identification of soil microorganisms – next-generation sequencing (NGS) technique.

Locations of soil sampling

Representative soil samples were collected by the ReLive project partners (Institute of Agrophysics PAS, Poland; University College Dublin, Ireland; Helmholtz Centre Potsdam GFZ, Germany; Universidad de Extremadura, Spain; Avoin association, Finlandia) at various locations across Europe, as shown on the map.

9 experiments

17 different soils

7 arable
+ 5 grasslands
+ 4 silvopasture
+ 2 forests

Sol samples were collected from areas with different land uses.

- Poland - arable fields
- Ireland - forests and grasslands
- Germany - arable fields
- Spain - silvopastoral system
- Finland - grasslands

List of experiments performed and variants of the experiment

No	Measured gases	Soil management variants	Tested soil - Country sampled / Land use / Crop	Climate Smart Action used – soil additives	Experiment conditions (temperature; soil moisture content)
1	Temp. sensitivity of CO ₂ emission (Q ₁₀)	no fertilization	Poland / Arable /Corn; Winter wheat	without and with biochar (produced from corn)	5/15°C; 15/25°C 60%; 100% WHC
		mineral fertilization			
		mineral fertilization + manure			
2	CH ₄ , CO ₂ , O ₂	no fertilization	Poland / Arable / Corn	without and with biochar (produced from corn)	15°C; 25°C 60%; 100% WHC
		mineral fertilization			
		mineral fertilization + manure			
3	CH ₄ , CO ₂ , O ₂	no fertilization	Poland / Arable / Winter wheat	without and with biochar (produced from corn)	15°C; 25°C 60%; 100% WHC
		mineral fertilization			
		mineral fertilization + manure			
4	CH ₄ , CO ₂ , O ₂	organic fertilization (manure)	Poland / Arable / Triticale	without any additives (control) with corn residues	25°C 60%; 100% WHC
		inorganic fertilization	Poland / Arable / Triticale	with biochar mix of corn residues + biochar with wheat residues mix of wheat residues + biochar	25°C 60%; 100% WHC
5	CH ₄ , CO ₂ , O ₂	no fertilization - tillage and no-till	Poland / Arable / Corn	without any additives (control) with corn residues	25°C 60%; 100% WHC
		reduced mineral N fert. - tillage and no-till		with biochar mix of corn residues + biochar	

		full mineral N fert. - tillage and no-till		with wheat residues mix of wheat residues + biochar	
6	CH ₄ , CO ₂ , O ₂	fertilization with digestate	Germany / Arable / Winter rye	without any additives (control) with corn residues with biochar mix of corn residues + biochar with wheat residues mix of wheat residues + biochar	25°C 60%; 100% WHC
7	CH ₄ , CO ₂ , O ₂		Ireland / Forests (2) + Grasslands (2)	without any additives (control) fir sawdust biochar corn biochar	25°C 60%; 100% WHC
8	CH ₄ , CO ₂ , O ₂		Finland / Grasslands (3)	without any additives (control) fir sawdust biochar corn biochar	25°C 60%; 100% WHC
9	CH ₄ , CO ₂ , O ₂		Spain / Silvopastoral systems (4) / Natural pastures + legume sown	without any additives (control) oak pruning residues biochar and activated with manure	25°C 60%; 100% WHC

Summary and challenges

The additives used in the experiments showed potential for increasing the CH₄ uptake capacity of the tested soils by altering their physicochemical parameters. This had effect on gases diffusion and the soil microorganism community, including CH₄-oxidizing methanotrophic bacteria. The challenge in practice is to select the appropriate doses of additives, the type of biochar and the method of its application to a specific type of soil with different uses and with various requirements. Considering CH₄ emissions from livestock farms, it is certainly worthwhile to implement methods that effectively increase CH₄ uptake by soils, which has the potential to improve the C balance at the farm level.

The more accurate results of the experiments are planned to be published in international journals.

Acknowledgements

This report was developed under the EU-ERA-Net ReLive project, which was supported by the Joint Call of the Cofund ERA-Nets SusCrop (Grant N° 771134), FACCE ERA-GAS (Grant N° 696356), ICT-AGRI-FOOD (Grant N° 862665) and SusAn (Grant N° 696231). The lab studies presented were financed by the Polish National Centre for Research and Development (CIRCULARITY/61/ReLive/2022) within the ReLive project: <https://relive-era.net/>

The report is the outcome of deliverable D4.2: “Report on Mitigation Potential of CSA for livestock farms across Europe: An assessment of the potential of different soils for CH₄ uptake and C sequestration, based on laboratory incubations, with the identification of soil parameters and microbiology as major drivers”.

References:

- Bhattacharyya P.N., Sandilya S.P., Sarma B. *et al.* 2024. Biochar as Soil Amendment in Climate-Smart Agriculture: Opportunities, Future Prospects, and Challenges. *J Soil Sci Plant Nutr* 24, 135–158. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42729-024-01629-9>
- Kubaczyński A., Walkiewicz A., Pytlak A. *et al.* 2022. Biochar dose determines methane uptake and methanotroph abundance in Haplic Luvisol. *Sci Tot Environ* 806, 151259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.151259>
- Maze M., Taqi M.O., Tolba R. *et al.* 2024. Estimation of methane greenhouse gas emissions from livestock in Egypt during 1989 to 2021. *Sci Rep* 14, 14992. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-63011-0>
- Schmidt H.P., Kammann C., Hagemann N. *et al.* 2021. Biochar in agriculture – A systematic review of 26 global meta-analyses. *GCB Bioenergy* DOI: 10.1111/gcbb.12889
- Walkiewicz A., Brzezińska M., Wnuk E., Jabłoński B. 2020. Soil properties and not high CO₂ affect CH₄ production and uptake in periodically waterlogged arable soils. *J Soils Sediments* 20:1231–1240. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-019-02525-x>
- Walkiewicz, A., Kalinichenko, K., Kubaczyński, A. *et al.* Usage of biochar for mitigation of CO₂ emission and enhancement of CH₄ consumption in forest and orchard Haplic Luvisol (Siltic) soils. *Appl Soil Eco* 156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2020.103711>